

STUDYING THE RESULTS OF MICROBIOLOGICAL RESEARCH FOR VULVAR CANCER

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Target

Studying the results of microbiological research for vulvar cancer

Materials and methods

We studied 161 patients with a confirmed diagnosis of cervical cancer who were treated in the conditions of the Russian National Medical Research Center .

Cultural or molecular methods (PCR) were used to determine sexually transmitted diseases and opportunistic infections . Samples were taken from the genitourinary tract, including the endocervix (obtained during a Pap test), as well as from urine for gonorrhea and chlamydial infections.

results

Microbiological examination of smears from the vulva revealed microorganisms characteristic of both the genitourinary system of women and the gastrointestinal tract .

We also conducted a study aimed at identifying the HPV virus, but unlike other researchers, we were not faced with the question of the role of HPV in the pathogenesis and prognosis of vulvar cancer, but of the need for antiviral therapy in this category of patients.

Conclusion

According to our data, at least more than 40% of patients with vulvar cancer require antiviral therapy. Thus, the complex of accompanying therapy in patients with a positive test for HPV must include antiviral drugs.

